

EXPLORERS

Exceed your limits.
Become the BEST.

URBAN.SYSTEMS

urban.systems

URBAN.SYSTEMS is a trusted “incubator” for local, state and federal governments in how to upgrade smart technology to support the needs, desires and expectations of their citizens, helping “scale” interoperable components through partnerships.

As cities explore new transit systems, roads and utilities or modernize their aging infrastructure URBAN.SYSTEMS and its partners, such as the Portland State University and Technology Association of Oregon, provide a range of civic engagement, financial, design, and software services that reduce cost, simplify design and financing, and build scalable operational management. Its team accounts long experience in Intel, the National Institute of Standards and Technology, IBM, Accenture, Philips Medical Systems and DaimlerChrysler.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGES

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Transportation
Energy
Wellbeing

CHALLENGE #8 - US-CITY-01

→ Smart City Architectures

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Implementing a pilot based on the consensus Framework for Smart City Architectures

OBJECTIVES

Develop and leave a lasting relationship between EU and US Smart City Architecture efforts

SKILLS REQUIRED

Understanding the challenges of an integrated smart city architecture

